

Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETERS

I7005E, I7298E, 19214E, 2614

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
Building 125, Cranfield University
Cranfield
Bedford
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Dr Hannah Price

DESCRIPTION: Four 50 Ω Rosemount Engineering platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs)

IDENTIFICATION: Type: EI02 AL (Loom), EI02BL (Loom), E102BL (Loom), E102AL (Loom)
Serial No: I7005E, I7298E, 19214E, 2614

PREVIOUS CERTIFICATES: I7005E : 2013060136-1 dated 1 August 2013
I7298E : Not previously calibrated at NPL
19214E : Not previously calibrated at NPL
2614 : 2013060136-2 dated 30 August 2013

DATES OF CALIBRATION: 19 November to 23 November 2015

Reference: 2015110037-2

Date of issue: 15 December 2015

Checked by:

Signed:

Name: Dr S A Bell

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

Continuation Sheet

MEASUREMENTS

As requested the platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs) were monitored using a precision resistance bridge with traceability to national standards, using an excitation current of 2 mA, and the resistance values obtained appear in the table below. At each generated condition a time of not less than 60 minutes was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. A set of 10 readings recorded at 1 minute intervals was then taken from the instruments under test.

The calibration was carried out in a test chamber, in air, against NPL reference thermometers. Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to ITS-90 through NPL Temperature Standards.

The values of the applied conditions are shown in the first column of the table below. The values measured from the instruments under test are then quoted with their equivalent expanded uncertainties, shown in degrees Celsius. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instruments.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and less than 80 % relative humidity.

Applied Condition	Test Thermometers							
	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial number I7005E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial number I7298E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial number 19214E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial number 2614	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
-60.02 #	38.236	± 0.10	38.293	± 0.10	38.321	± 0.10	38.609	± 0.10
-50.00 #	40.281	± 0.10	40.342	± 0.10	40.373	± 0.10	40.677	± 0.10
-40.00	42.316	± 0.08	42.380	± 0.08	42.415	± 0.08	42.734	± 0.08
-29.95	44.352	± 0.08	44.420	± 0.08	44.457	± 0.08	44.793	± 0.08
-20.03	46.356	± 0.05	46.423	± 0.05	46.467	± 0.05	46.819	± 0.05
-10.01	48.373	± 0.05	48.449	± 0.05	48.492	± 0.05	48.858	± 0.05
+ 0.00	50.383	± 0.05	50.462	± 0.05	50.508	± 0.05	50.890	± 0.05
+ 9.89	52.363	± 0.05	52.446	± 0.05	52.495	± 0.05	52.892	± 0.05
+20.00	54.379	± 0.05	54.465	± 0.05	54.518	± 0.05	54.930	± 0.05
+30.07	56.383	± 0.05	56.474	± 0.05	56.528	± 0.05	56.956	± 0.05
+39.89	58.329	± 0.05	58.422	± 0.05	58.482	± 0.05	58.924	± 0.05
+50.17	60.361	± 0.05	60.458	± 0.05	60.520	± 0.05	60.979	± 0.05

NOTE: # All points below $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are outside the range of UKAS accreditation of NPL for air temperature

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UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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